

BURN-OUT AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF EXTENSION WORKERS IN BENUE AGRICULTURAL AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY (BNARDA) FOR FOOD SECURITY

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates burn-out and job performance of extension service workers in Benue Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (BNARDA). Population consists all extension workers in BNARDA. 3ZEOs, 7AEOs, 100BESs, 40BEAs, 200VEAs and 50SMSs were purposively selected which form sample size of 400. Data were collected using structured questionnaire. Frequency, percentages and mean were used to analyze the objectives, logistic regression's chi-square statistics to test hypothesis one, and Mann Whitney (U) to test hypothesis two. Findings of the study revealed that the mean age of extension workers was 45years. 55.6% of extension workers were males, 44.4% females. Extension workers were mostly married (93.7%); educated (60.3%) and experienced (67.6%). 30.8% male extension workers experienced high level of burn-out, 20.0% female's experienced high burn-out. Motivation through regular payment of salaries (91.7) was ranked 1st as factor that reduced burn-out. Logit regression analysis showed education ($x^2 = -3.314$); household size ($x^2 = 1.130$) and income ($x^2 = 0.000$) had significant effect on extension workers level of burn-out at 0.05% of probability. There was significant difference in level of burn-out of BEA's and VEA's ($p < 0.005$). There was significant difference in level of burn-out of male and female extension workers at 0.05% of significant. The study recommends that burn-out of extension workers be tackled by giving them financial and non-financial aids to assist them cope better with burn-out in the long run.

Keywords: Burn-Out, Job Performance, Extension, Food Security

INTRODUCTION

Food security, according to Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2001), is the access by all people at all times of enough food for an active healthy living. Age (2009) connotes food security as the availability, accessibility, affordability and utility of enough nutritious food by all people at all times for an active healthy life. Food security has taken great contrary position because the rate of growth in the area of agricultural production has not in any way met the growing demands of the population.

Agricultural extension services help farmers to identify and link with research on their production problems by providing awareness on opportunities for improvement of farm yields leading to increased income and better standard of living (Agbam, 2008). Samah, D'silva, Shafiril, & Uli (2010) noted that the mission of agricultural extension services is to provide research based information, educational programs and technology on farmers' needs and enabling them to make

informed decisions about their economic, social and cultural wellbeing. Most farmers in Nigeria depend on public extensions for information (Anaeto, Asiabaka, & Nnadi, 2012).

Ashil & Rod (2011) burn-out is a syndrome of inappropriate attitudes towards people and towards one self, often associated with uncomfortable physical and emotional symptoms ranging from exhaustion and insomnia to migraine headache and ulcer. Continual deterioration of insomnia to migraine headache and ulcer reduces individual performance is frequent element in the syndrome. Mayo (2012) burn-out is the inability to cope with the stresses of extension work and personal lives.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Growing lack of job security had made burn-out a common risk to the health and well being of both men and women in all occupation particularly extension services (Mayo, 2012). Ashil & Rod (2011) opined that extension workers who are less satisfied with their jobs encounter burn-out more than those who are adequately satisfied. Gondo, Yaro, & Pev, (2018) examined the Effect of Burn-out on Innovation Preference among Rural Farmers in Benue State; Gondo, Gyata, & Pev (2020) examined Burn-out on Adoption of Innovations among Small Scale Farmers in Benue State, it seems little or nothing is known about Burn-Out and Job Performance of Extension services of Benue Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (BNARDA).

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study was to investigate burn-out and job performance of extension services in Benue Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (BNARDA) for food security in Benue State. Specifically, the objectives are to:

1. Describe the socio-economic characteristics of extension workers in BNARDA affected by burn-out;
2. Determine the level of burn-out of male and female extension workers in BNARDA.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions are pertinent in this study:

1. What are the socio-economic characteristics of extension workers in BNARDA affected by burn-out?
2. What is the level of burn-out of male and female extension workers in BNARDA?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between level of burn-out and socio-economic characteristics of extension workers in BNARDA.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the level of burn-out of male and female extension workers in BNARDA.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There is a clear relationship between age and burn-out (Ashil & Rod, 2011). Burn-out seems to be greatest when helping professionals are young and least for older workers. Although young people usually have less work experience than their older counterparts, the effect of age on burn-out reflects more than just the duration on the job. The implication here is the people in any helping professional have difficulty in dealing with problems of burn-out when they are young and new to the job, may leave the profession entirely and because of this early dropout, they will not be around in later years. This means

that the older one who survived, remain, do well in the profession and consequently report less burn-out than their younger counterparts.

Jamasari, Jasmine, Norhamideh, Suwaiba, & Nordin (2012) maintain that the youths and Middle Ages dominate agricultural extension work. Age of agricultural extension workers is an important factor in determining the effectiveness of agricultural extension services.

The sex of the individual does not seem to have relationship to burn-out. Ashil & Rod (2011) noted that while males and females are fairly similar in their experience of burn-out a few differences exist. These differences are that males show slightly more of one aspect of burn-out, and females shows slightly another. In the past, extension work was reserved for men only believing that it was only men that were farmers and that male agents were needed to lead them (Jamasari, Jasmine, Norhamideh, Suwaiba, & Nordin (2012). However, the fact that women are also farmers and needed to be reached in order to achieve increased productivity has necessitated the employment of female extension workers who are believed to be in a better position to do the job of reaching women.

According to Mayo (2012) burn-out has a consistent relationship with marital status, while helping professionals who are single experienced the most burn-out, their married counterparts experienced the least. Ashil & Rod (2011) have postulated several reasons why people with families are less vulnerable to burn-out. Firstly, they are older, stable and more mature psychologically. Secondly, the presence of their families or their involvement with their lives helps them deal with personal problems and emotional conflicts. Thirdly, to the individual, the family is often an emotional resource rather than an emotional drain. The love and constant support of family members help individuals cope with the emotional demands of work. The individual with a family to support becomes more realistically concerned about job security, salary and benefits as compared to the single employee who feel freer to move about.

Mayo (2012) maintained that masters level degree holders in the profession tend to burn-out less frequently than workers with lower degrees. Mayo (2012) also found that Professionals with post graduate training such as those with doctorates enjoy good pay, job security and tenure. Samah, D'silva, Shafril & Uli (2010) maintained that level of formal education is a strong predictor of work performance.

Mayo (2012) reported that long years of service means that enough experience would have been developed and could be passed down to subordinate on the job. Samah, D'silva, Shafril & Uli (2010) have shown that in the years of agricultural extension workers in execution of their duties. Experienced agricultural extension workers tend to perform extension work with ease.

Ashil & Rod (2011) explained that, wage is a source of off-farm income, and this variable captures non-agricultural activities to diversify income sources. Remittances, as an indicator of networks outside the community are also a rural-urban linkage indicator. Now, on the current direction of study and investigation, it is important to gauge the livelihood strategies employed by household's members and how their livelihood resources and assets are used. Enhanced incentive is an important motivator to the average individual. This is in agreement with Mayo (2012) who reported that adequate motivation is important sustenance of staff morale.

The socio-economic characteristics of extension workers (A) are linked with burn-out by line of relationship, while level of burn-out of male extension workers (B) is also linked to burn-out. The level of burn-out of female extension workers (C) is also linked to burn-out.

METHODOLOGY

Benue State was created on 3rd February, 1976 and derives its name from River Benue, which is one of the largest river in the country and the most outstanding geographic feature in the state. Benue State has twenty three (23) Local Government Areas. The Tiv speaking areas have fourteen (14) LGAs while the Idoma & Igede areas have nine (9) LGAs. These Local Government Areas are: Ado, Agatu, Apa, Buruku, Gboko, Guma, Gwer, Gwer-west, Katsina-Ala, Konshisha, Kwande, Logo, Makurdi, Obi, Ogbadibo, Ohimini, Oju, Okpokwo, Otukpo, Tarka, Ukum, Ushongo and Vandeikya. Benue State has land mass of 33,955 square kilometres and lies between latitude 6.50⁰ and 880⁰ North and longitudes 7.47⁰North and 10.00⁰East (Benue State Government, 2012).

The State is bounded on the West by Kogi and Enugu States and Taraba State to the East, Cross River State to the South and Nasarawa State to the North and shares an international boundary in the Republic of Cameroun on the South east (Benue State Government, 2012). The ecology of Benue state supports extensive arable crops and livestock production as well as fruits, palm, grains, legumes, roots and tuber production; hence the state is acclaimed the Food Basket of Nigeria. Benue state accounts for over 70% of the country's soybean yield and also produces large quantities of vegetables such as tomatoes, pepper, okra and so on (Benue state Government,2012).

Benue state has a population of 4,253,641 (FRN, 2009). The sex analysis shows that there are 2,144,043 males and 2,109,598 females. This makes the state the ninth most populous in the country. Over 80% of this population derives its livelihood from agriculture with more than 70% of the populace living in the rural areas. The State is populated by several ethnic groups: Tiv, Idoma, Igede, Etulo, Jukun, Ufia, Orring, Abakpa, Igbo, Akweya and Nyifon.

The population for this study consisted of all extension workers in Benue Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (BNARDA).The state has three (3) Zone Extension Officers (ZEOs), seven (7) Area Extension Officers (AEOs), one hundred (100) Block Extension Supervisors (BESs), forty (40) Block Extension Agents (BEAs), two hundred (200) Village Extension Agents (VEAs) and fifty(50) Subject Matter Specialists (SMSs), totalling four hundred (400) all spread across the zones.

A purposive sampling technique was carried out in the three (3) agricultural zones namely: Benue Central, Benue East, and Benue North. Data for this study were generated from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected through the use of a well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire for the study consisted of three (3) sections: A (socio-economic characteristics of extension workers of BNARDA), B (level of burn-out of male extension workers of BNARDA), C (level of burn-out of female extension workers of BNARDA).

Research instrument was validated by passing it through two (2) Professors who are research experts in the Department of Agricultural Extension & Communication, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi (JOSTUM) Benue State and by pilot-testing to ensure that it possesses both content and face validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined by using the scores obtained from pilot-testing which were correlated using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient for scores at the interval level, while the Spearman's Rank (rho) Correlation was used for scores obtained at the ordinal level.

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, percentages, mean as well as inferential statistics such as Logistic Regression, Chi-square statistics and Mann Whitney (U) test. Descriptive statistics such as frequency distribution, percentages and mean were used to analyze objective 1, 2 and 3, while Inferential statistics such as Logistic Regression, Chi-square statistics were used to test hypothesis 1 and Mann Whitney (U) test was used to test hypothesis 2.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What are the socio-economic characteristics of extension workers in BNARDA affected by burn-out?

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Agricultural Extension Workers in BNARDA

Socio-Economic Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Age (Year)			
27-32	6	1.5	
33-38	20	5.0	
39-44	100	25.0	
45-50	202	50.5	
51-56	71	17.75	
≥ 57	1	0.25	
Sub-total (a)	400	100.0	45.69
Sex			
Male	250	62.5	
Female	150	37.5	
Sub-total (b)	400	100.0	1.44
Marital status			
Married	300	75.0	
Single	100	25.0	
Sub-total (c)	400	100.0	1.06
Highest educational qualification (years)			
OND	80	20.0	
NCE	5	1.25	
Degree/HND	250	62.5	
PGD	25	6.25	
MSc	40	10.0	
Sub-total (d)	400	100.0	15.83
Work experience (years)			
1-10	18	4.5	
11-20	305	76.25	
21-30	8	2.0	
≥31	69	17.25	
Sub-total (e)	400	100.0	16.73
Household size (number)			
1-3	20	5.0	
4-7	310	77.5	
≥8	70	17.5	
Sub-total (f)	400	100.0	5.44
Income (naira) (per annum)			
400,000-500,000	15	3.75	
501,000-601,000	10	2.5	
602,000-702,000	60	15.0	
703,000-803,000	250	62.5	
804,000-904,000	40	10.0	
≥905,000	25	6.25	
Sub-total (h)	400	100	37.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 indicates that 50.5% of the respondents were above 45 years of age while 25.0% of them were between 39-44 years. This implies that the extension workers were mostly middle aged showing that extension services is dominated by those still in their most productive years and mature enough to carry out extension work. The table also indicates that 62.5% of the extension workers were males while 37.5% were females. This implies that the ratio of male extension workers to the females were not much. Furthermore, majority (93.7%) of extension workers were married and responsible, while 6.3% were single.

Research Question Two: What is the level of burn-out of male and female extension workers in BNARDA?

Table 2: Level of Burn-out of Male and Female Extension Workers in BNARDA

Variables	Males (n=250)			Females (n=150)		
	High (%)	Low (%)	None (%)	High (%)	Low (%)	None (%)
Tired and drained most of the time	22 (31.4)	33 (47.1)	15 (21.4)	25 (44.6)	10 (17.8)	14 (25.0)
Lowered immunity	6 (8.5)	27 (38.5)	33 (47.1)	1 (1.7)	27 (48.2)	27 (48.2)
Frequent headache, back pain, Muscle ache	20 (28.5)	12 (17.1)	27 (38.5)	23 (41.0)	8 (14.2)	24 (42.8)
Change in appetite of sleep habit	22 (31.4)	24 (34.2)	19 (27.1)	0 (0.0)	16 (28.5)	40 (71.4)
Sense of failure and self doubt	23 (32.8)	8 (11.4)	33 (47.1)	19 (33.9)	5 (8.9)	31 (55.3)
Helpless, trapped and defeated	22 (31.4)	12 (17.1)	30 (42.8)	1 (3.5)	7 (10.7)	37 (66.0)
Detachment, feeling of loneliness	22 (31.4)	8 (11.4)	39 (55.7)	2 (3.5)	6 (10.7)	43 (76.7)
Loss of motivation	34 (48.5)	15 (21.4)	14 (20.0)	27 (48.2)	7 (12.5)	20 (35.7)
Increased cynical or negative outlook	26 (37.1)	9 (12.8)	28 (40.0)	24 (42.8)	1 (1.7)	31 (55.3)
Decreased satisfaction and sense of accomplishment	20 (28.5)	25 (35.7)	19 (27.1)	2 (3.5)	35 (62.5)	19 (33.9)
Withdrawal from responsibilities	22 (31.4)	11 (15.7)	31 (44.2)	20 (35.7)	5 (8.9)	31 (55.3)
Isolation from others	21 (30.0)	13 (18.5)	30 (42.8)	0 (0.0)	7 (12.5)	49 (87.5)
Procrastination, taking longer to get things done	21 (30.0)	29 (41.4)	14 (20.0)	20 (35.0)	11 (19.6)	23 (41.0)
Use of food, drug or alcohol to cope	18 (25.7)	10 (14.2)	41 (58.5)	0 (0.0)	2 (3.5)	54 (96.4)
Takes out frustration on others	7 (10.0)	24 (34.2)	28 (40.0)	20 (35.7)	6 (10.7)	29 (51.7)
Skip work or come in late and Leave early	3 (4.2)	28 (40.0)	34 (48.5)	0 (0.0)	4 (7.1)	50 (89.2)
Decreased communication	21 (30.0)	25 (35.7)	20 (28.5)	0 (0.0)	12 (21.4)	44 (78.5)

Multiple responses recorded

Table 2 revealed that less than average of the male extension workers experienced high level of burn-out. The highest symptom experienced was loss of motivation (48.5%), followed by increased negative outlook (37.1%), sense of failure and self doubt (32.8%), tiredness and drained most of the time (31.4%), change in appetite or sleep habit (31.4%), decreased self communication (30.0%). As low as 8.5% experience of lowered immunity, 10.0% takes out frustration on others and 4.2% skipping work were recorded at high level. The extensions did not respond to some of the questions. A good number of males did not experience use of food, drug and alcohol to cope (58.5%), detachment and feeling of loneliness (55.7%), skipping work or come late and leave early (48.2%), isolation from others (42.8%), increased cynical and negative outlook (40.0%), frequent headache, back and muscle pain (38.5%). Table 2 further shows 47.1%, 41.1%, 40.0%, 38.5% and 35.7% of male extensions experienced tiredness and drained most of the time, procrastination, skip work or come in late and leave early, lowered immunity, decreased satisfaction/change in appetite or sleep habit respectively on low account.

Few female extension workers experienced high level of burn-out (Table 2). The highest experience recorded was loss of motivation (48.2%) followed by tiredness and drained most of the time (44.6%), increased negative outlook (42.8%), frequent headache, back and muscle pain (41.0%). It shows majority of the females did not experience use of drugs and alcohol to cope (96.4%), skipping work or come in early and leave late (89.2%), isolation from others (87.5%), decreased

communication (78.5%), detachment and loneliness (79.7%), change in appetite or sleep habit (71.4%), helplessness and defeat (66.0%), withdrawal from responsibilities (55.3%). Table 2 indicated that a good number of the females experienced decreased satisfaction (62.5%) and lowered immunity (48.2%) on low account. 30.8% of the males experienced high burn-out while 29.3% experienced low burn-out meaning that majority (60%) experienced burn-out. 20.0% of the females experienced high level of burn-out and 18.3% had low experience.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between level of burn-out and socio-economic characteristics of extension workers in BNARDA.

Table 3: Logit Regression of Selected Socio-economic Characteristics of Extension Workers Level of Burn-out

Variables	B	S.E	Wald	P-vale
Age	-0.112	0.104	1.156	0.282
Sex	1.710	1.049	2.655	0.103
Education	-3.314	0.861	14.815*	0.000
Work Experience	-0.169	0.119	2.021	0.155
Household size	1.130	0.483	5.477**	0.019
Income	0.000	0.000	7.672*	0.006
Constant	25.207	9.044	7.768	0.005

Source: Field Survey, 2024

* Significant at 0.05%, Nagelkerke R square = 0.604, Chi square = 59.339*, Sig. = 0.000

Logistic regression model was used to assess the effect of socio-economic characteristics of extension workers on their level of burn-out as presented on table 3. From the result, Nagelkerke $R^2 = 0.604$. This means that the individual variables accounted for 60.4% of the variations in the level of burn-out of extension workers. The Chi square statistics was significant ($p < 0.05$) implying that the socio-economic characteristics had significant effect on the level of burn-out of extension workers. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternate accepted. Hence, it was concluded that socio-economic characteristics have significant effect on the level of burn-out of the extension workers.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the level of burn-out of male and female extension workers in BNARDA

Table 4: Mann Whitney Analysis of Burn-out Level of Male and Female Extension Workers in BNARDA

Variables	Males		Females	
	Freq	R ₁	Freq	R ₂
Tired and drained most of the time	22	23	25	29
Lowered immunity	6	10	1	5.5
Frequent headache, back pain, muscle ache	20	15.5	23	26.5
Change in appetite or sleep habit	22	23	0	2.5
Sense of failure and self doubt	23	26.5	19	13
Helpless, trapped and defeat	22	23	1	5.5
Detachment, feeling of loneliness	22	23	2	7.5
Loss of motivation	34	33	27	32
Increased cynical or negative outlook	26	30.5	24	28
Decreased satisfaction and sense of accomplishment	20	15.5	2	7.5
Withdrawal from responsibilities	22	23	20	15.5
Isolation from others	21	19	0	2.5
Procrastination, taking longer to get things done	21	19	20	15.5
Use of food, drug or alcohol to cope	18	12	0	2.5
Takes out frustration on others	7	11	26	30.5
Skip work or come in late and leave early	3	9	0	2.5
Decreased communication	21	19	0	2.5
	N ₁ =17	ΣR ₁ =335	N ₁ =17	ΣR ₁ =260
	U ₁ =181			

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 shows that there is significant difference between male and female extension workers of BNARDA in terms of burn-out ($p < 0.05$). The Mann-Whitney test shows that U_1 calculated (181) $>$ Critical U value (0) at 0.05 level of significance. It reveals further that $\Sigma R_1 = 335.0$, while $\Sigma R_2 = 260.0$. This implies that there is a significant difference in the level of burn-out of the male and female extension workers of BNARDA. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings with respect to research question one indicates that the extension workers were mostly middle aged showing that extension services is dominated by those still in their most productive years and mature enough to carry out extension work. This agrees with Jamasari, Jasmine, Norhamideh, Suwaiba, & Nordin, (2012) that the youths and middle ages dominate extension work. Age of extension workers is an important factor in determining the effectiveness of extension services. The study also revealed that the ratio of male extension workers to the females were not much. In the past, agricultural extension work was reserved for men only believing that it was only men that were farmers and that male agents needed to lead them (Samah, D'silva, Shafril & Uli, 2010). However, the fact that women are also farmers and needed to be reached in order to achieve increased productivity has necessitated the employment of female extension workers who are believed to be in a better position to do the job of reaching women. The study further revealed that majority (93.7%) of extension workers were married and responsible, while 6.3% were single. This is in agreement with Ashil & Rod (2011).

Findings also showed that 60.3% of the respondents had Higher National Diploma (HND), followed by 23% of them with Ordinary National Diploma (OND) in various specialties of agriculture. This implies that extension workers were qualified for their job. This will aid effective performance of their duties. This agrees with Samah, D'silva, Shafril, & Uli (2010) that the level of formal education is a strong predictor of work performance. 67.6% of extension workers had between 11-20 years of working experience, 15.0% had above 31 years of working experience while 11.2% of them had 5-10 years of working experience (Table 1). This indicates that most of extension workers had considerably worked for a long period to be able to know their job description better and perform appreciably well. Ashil & Rod (2011) reported that long years of service means that enough experience would have been developed and could be passed down to subordinate on the job. Samah, D'silva, Shafril & Uli (2010) have shown that in the years of extension workers in execution of their duties. Experienced extension workers tend to perform extension work with ease. Hence, the wealth of experience acquired contributes immensely to the efficiency and ease with which the extension workers carried out their duties. 59.0% of the extension workers had 4-7 persons in their households. It is likely that additional responsibilities from the family could affect their performance negatively. This is more especially when the family is large and unplanned. Hence, the attention of extension workers tends to be divided between his families. 36.6% of extension workers earned about ₦703,000 – 803,000, 12.8% earned within the range of ₦804,000 – 904,000 with a negligible 8.0% earn above ₦905,000. This implies that extension workers earn enough to keep them comfortable at work. Enhanced incentive is an important motivator to the average individual. This is in agreement with Mayo (2012) who reported that adequate motivation is important to sustain staff morale.

Test of hypothesis relating to research question one showed that education significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced probability of high burn-out. This implied that the extension workers with lower qualification performed better than those who had acquired more education. This may be because they need to work harder to enable them rise and get promotion. Additionally, Household size significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased the probability of high burn-out. This implies that extension

workers with larger household sizes most likely burn-out. It may be that more members in the household could be a source of inspiration. This finding contradicts the submission of Mayo (2012) that extension workers with small family size will more likely burn-out compared to their counterparts who have large family size. Furthermore, Income significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the probability of high burn-out. The implication of this findings is that the higher the income of the extension workers the lower the level of burn-out. This is because income is a good motivator. Ashil & Rod (2011) maintained that adequate motivation is important for sustained staff morale.

Findings of the study with respect to research question two showed that only 38.3% of the females experienced burn-out. The implication is that the male extension workers experienced more burn-out than the females. This is consistent with a similar study by Jamasari, Jasmine, Norhamideh, Suwaiba & Nordin (2012). The test of hypothesis in this direction also revealed that there is a significant difference in the level of burn-out of the male and female extension workers of BNARDA. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. It implies that the level at which the male and female extension workers breakdown mentally and physically differs. This agrees with Mayo (2012) that there is a significant difference among employees' burn-out in terms of sex.

CONCLUSION

The study investigates burn-out and job performance of extension services in BNARDA for food security in Benue State, Nigeria. The study established that socio-economic characteristics had significant effect on the level of burn-out of extension workers. It is therefore concluded that effective job performance for food security will occur when burn-out is low and this can only be possible if the extensions are given both financial and non financial encouragement to reduce occurrence of burn-out.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is therefore recommended that there is an urgent need to tackle the issue of burn-out of extension workers for food security by given them both financial and non-financial encouragement and also particularly, that women should be assisted by their husbands to share household chores and family responsibilities to support their career development. This will assist them to cope better with burn-out in the long run.

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